

Web application to reduce teen depression with eating disorder and mental related problems

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Abstract: The most serious issues with teenagers are mental health and eating disorders. In the world, 14% of those between the ages of 10 and 19 struggle with mental illness and eating problems. Adolescence is a critical time for forming social and emotional habits that are necessary for mental health. These include adopting healthy sleep patterns; exercising regularly; developing coping, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills; and learning to manage emotions. It is crucial to create safe and encouraging conditions in the home, at school, and in the larger community. Also, Adolescents are becoming more frequently affected by eating disorders, which are complicated illnesses. With an incidence of up to 5% and a rate that has drastically climbed over the past three decades, they rank as the third most prevalent chronic illness among adolescent females. So, creating a social media platform where persons struggling with eating disorders and mental health issues can go to discuss their inner feelings and express their opinions is how we, as social entrepreneurs, plan to address this issue. So that we could specifically assess each of their issues and give them the appropriate advice .Even though it is a small business, it will have a significant impact on young people who are not in stable mental and emotional health.

Keywords: mental health condition, eating disorders, teenagers, social media platform

Introduction

Adolescents must have strong physical and mental health in order to develop. Establish healthy sleep and exercise routines as well as coping, problem- solving, and interpersonal skills [1, 2]. Develop emotional restraint. It is essential to establish secure and supportive environments at home, in the classroom, and in the greater community [3]. Eating disorders continue to be one of the most important disorders affecting a significant proportion of adolescents and young adults [4]. The prevalence of eating disorders, especially Binge eating disorders, is on the rise and has caused significant problems because of the associated comorbidities [5]. Although recent research has shown that the prevalence in males was previously underestimated, these disorders do have a clear female preponderance [6].

Eating disorders are observed to have become more common in western cultures in the second half of the twentieth century in young women.

Several factors have an impact on mental health [7]. The likelihood of social isolation, discrimination, and stigma for adolescents with anxiety, mood, attention, and behaviour disorders is high, which may influence their willingness to seek therapy [8, 9]. Also, they are more likely to struggle academically, engage in risky behaviour, develop medical ailments, and witness human rights violations [10].

Early adulthood or adolescence is common starting points for eating disorders. Teenage girls experience them more frequently than teenage boys; however they can also affect them [11]. These might seriously affect a teen's general welfare and put them under a lot of stress. Among the social effects include isolation and low self-esteem [12]. Eating disorders can result in severe health problems that can be fatal. Many signs and symptoms of eating problems can appear [13]. Though they aren't always evident, they occasionally are. To hide an eating disorder, people frequently go to considerable lengths [14]. We are aiding youngsters by providing guidance on how to tackle these difficulties as entrepreneurs because youth represent the future of the country [15].

Eating Disorder

Psychological illnesses known as eating disorders, such as anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge eating disorder, cause severe abnormalities in eating behaviour [16]. Teens with anorexia struggle to maintain a healthy weight. Bulimia is characterised by recurrent binge eating episodes that are followed by compulsive actions like vomiting or the use of laxatives to purge the body of food [18]. Unrestrained overeating is a hallmark of binge eating.

One in 100 females may suffer from anorexia nervosa [17]. Teenagers who have anorexia are at least 15% underweight and fear gaining weight. People think their physical image is the primary indicator of their self-worth [19].

According to experts, a large number of American girls struggle with bulimia and have hid the issue [20]. Bulimia frequently begins in late adolescence or early adulthood. Bulimic individuals go through cycles of binge eating followed by purging through vomiting, laxative or diuretic use, or hours of aerobic exercise [21].

Bulimia warning indicators include

Excessive worry about being overweight, Diet restrictions followed by calorie-dense eating sprees, when feeling down, overeating, Feeling uncontrollable, After-meal disappearance depressive emotions, Overuse of drugs or alcohol, frequent intake of diuretics or laxatives, Exercise in excess, irregular cycles of menstruation [22]

An eating disorder might have many different causes. Researchers connect eating disorders to a variety of causes, including heredity, psychological issues, and familial dynamics [23]. The teen can be obsessed with becoming skinny and have low self-esteem [24].

Being a teen athlete in a lean-focused discipline like ballet, gymnastics, or running is occasionally linked to eating problems [25]. In one study, researchers found a connection between anorexia and a fixation with perfectionism, including worry about making mistakes, having high standards for oneself, and facing criticism from parents [27].

The Signs and Symptoms of Adolescent Eating Disorders

A misperception of one's body, largely skipping meals, Unusual dietary practises (such as eating thousands of calories at one meal or skipping meals), Periodic weighing, Extreme changes in weight, Insomnia, Constipation Dry skin or a skin rash, Decay in the teeth, Enamel erosion in the teeth, and Lower quality of the nails or hair, High levels of agitation and interest in exercising [29]

Mental illness in teens

Contrary to popular belief, teens are more susceptible to mental illness. But many types of mental illness are treatable; all that is needed is a thorough diagnosis [26]. When diagnosing someone with severe depressive disorder, doctors frequently look for a downbeat attitude or a lack of interest in hobbies or leisure pursuits [28]. Yet, similar symptoms can also be seen in teenagers as changes in their academic performance, a lack of interest in their friends, or an out-of-character annoyance. The consideration of additional criteria begins when at least one of the symptoms is present [30].

In addition, five of the following seven signs and symptoms must exist before a diagnosis can be made:

Changes in sleep habits, Guilt feelings that come on suddenly, Changes in energy levels, Changes in focus or efficiency, Changes in appetite, Changes in motivation, and Thoughts of suicide [31]

It's usually nothing to worry about if your teen periodically loses it or stays up late. On the other hand, if these feelings persist or if you experience any more unusual symptoms, it is typically a good idea to visit your doctor [32]. Unfortunately, most teenagers are hesitant to talk to their parents or doctors about their problems [33]. Because of this, a group of adults made the decision to launch this company to make it easier for teenagers to discuss their worries with people who are more like themselves [34].

Teenage mental disorders types

The following mental diseases are most prevalent in teens are Anxiety in general refers to persistent, excessive worry. Extreme feelings of insecurity and self-consciousness in social circumstances are known as social phobias. The hallmarks of depression include persistent gloom, anxiety and emptiness [35]

Common mental health conditions

Little children experience the same variety of mental health concerns as adults. Nonetheless, among American tweens and teens, the following mental health conditions are most frequently seen [37]. Between the ages of 3 and 17 in America, attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder affects around 10% of children (ADHD). About 9.5% of people experience anxiety, which makes it difficult to go about regular tasks [36]. Depression affects 4.5 percent of the population. Adolescent depression might or might not look like the traditional weeping blues [38]. Occasionally, the symptoms of sadness are more like those of rage or impatience [39]. Although less common, eating disorders like anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa can have a major negative impact on a person's health in their teens or early adulthood. Another significant problem that affects tweens and teens is self-harm, which is probably underreported [40].

Teens with eating disorders

Teenage years (between the ages of 12 and 18) are a time of fast physical, psychological, and social transformation that can bring forth both opportunities and difficulties. While some teenagers adjust quite easily to this period of transition, others may find it difficult.

Teenagers are prone to worry and concern. Teens with eating disorders, however, could have worries and fears that get stronger and gradually take over their life [41]. They might be concerned about things like not having friends, how to balance job and school obligations, their appearance, a family breakup, dating, bullying, and future plans, among others. Teenagers who have eating disorders display evidence of internal conflict [42].

Eating disorders conditions

One's physical health suffers as a result of these severe mental diseases. The following are the eating disorders that are most common:

A person with anorexia nervosa restricts their food intake because they are worried about gaining weight and have a distorted opinion of their looks [43]. A person with bulimia nervosa overeats enormous amounts of

food before purging it, possibly through vomiting, the use of laxatives, diuretics, or enemas. Because they don't eat a wide variety of foods, people with avoidant restricted food intake disorder (ARFID) don't obtain all the nutrients they need.

A person with a binge eating problem eats enormous amounts of food, feels guilty about it, but doesn't make any effort to quit [44]. In contrast to binge eating disorder, anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, or ARFID, disordered eating is behaviour that is not as extreme.

Warning symptoms of an eating disorder

If eating disorder behaviours are not recognised and treated, they can lead to serious physical and emotional problem.

Some signs that your teen might be having an eating disorder and needs prompt help include the ones listed below:

Depressed, irritated, and socially isolated. A great deal of attention paid to food, calories, or "healthy eating." Frequent remarks about how big and ugly they are. Limiting one's dietary consumption [45]. Giving reasons why you're not eating. Significant weight gain or loss (regardless of previous weight). Prolonged exercise. Constantly eating a lot of food in a short amount of time. Eating discreetly, late at night, or alone. Using laxatives or diet pills. Immediately using the restroom after eating.

Web applications

Eating disorders are a serious mental health concern that affect millions of people worldwide. Fortunately, there are a variety of web applications available that can help individuals who are struggling with these disorders. In this review article, we will examine some of the most popular web applications for eating disorders [46].

1. Recovery Record: Recovery Record is an app designed to help individuals with eating disorders stay on track with their recovery goals. The app provides a variety of tools, including meal planning, mood tracking, and goal setting. Users can also connect with a support team of professionals and loved ones for additional guidance and motivation.
2. Rise Up and Recover: Rise Up and Recover is a web application that provides a variety of features to help individuals with eating disorders manage their symptoms [47]. The app includes a meal planner, goal setting, and journaling tools, as well as a community forum for support and encouragement.
3. NOURISH: NOURISH is an app that focuses on providing education and guidance to individuals with eating disorders. The app includes a variety of resources, including educational articles, meal planning tools, and a support forum. Users can also connect with a licensed therapist for additional support.
4. Recovery Warriors: Recovery Warriors is a web application designed to help individuals with eating disorders build a supportive community. The app includes a variety of features, including a meal planner, goal setting tools, and a community forum for support and encouragement [48]. Users can also access educational resources and connect with a professional therapist for additional guidance.
5. EDANZ: EDANZ is a web application that provides a variety of resources and support to individuals with eating disorders. The app includes a meal planner, educational resources, and a support forum for individuals to connect with others who are also struggling with eating disorders. Users can also connect with a licensed therapist for additional guidance and support.

About our web application

The development of web applications to address teen depression with eating disorders and other mental health-related problems is an important and timely endeavour. With the rise of mental health issues among teenagers, it is crucial to develop innovative and effective ways to address these issues and provide support to those who need it.

The main objective of our project is to create a comfort space for teenagers dealing with mental stress caused by eating disorders [49]. The stigma around eating disorder caused by parent's and friend's inability to understand the disorder properly forces the victims to share and express their problems. It is often proved that talking to people about the cause of our stress will help us to cope and heal from it. When teenagers find their problems relatable to each other, it is proved to provide them some comfort and release their stress. So by creating a confidential space for people suffering from this disorder will allow the teenagers to express and release their stress.

They will also come to know various remedies and helping tips from fellow survivors. We will also hold therapy sessions so that we will come to know the teenagers who are seriously affected by this disorder. We can also prevent the uprising depression by holding private therapy session which will be available anytime. Our platform is available and open for anyone, irrespective of their disorder, to seek help and talk about it.

We will create a network of professional psychologists with specialty in various mental disorders and teenagers suffering from it. We are basically a brokerage company receiving commission from the teenagers joining the platform. We are planning to set a minimum fee to pay when the teenager definitely needs medical help [50]. Anyone can talk about their problems in anonymous ids with no cost, in this way we will gain their trust. General advice and motivation is free of cost.

Conclusion

Our main motto is to provide clinically superior continuous care, this application is basically a social service done in minimum cost for teenagers who aren't capable of sharing their problems with their first circle. We hope to create a trustworthy and confidential space for teenagers. This is the basic idea behind our start-up. We will be going large scale when we gain recognition among various teenagers suffering from mental disorders. Our platform will also help create awareness about this disorder among parents and friends, hence, providing the suffering teenagers a comfort space and support in their home. We hope to play a small part in putting future generation in a right path and support them as much as possible. Even though our application is a business, we hope to help as many as teenagers suffering from this disorder to overcome and heal from it. Overall, creating a web application to reduce teen depression with eating disorders and other mental health-related problems requires a collaborative effort involving mental health professionals, designers, developers, and teenagers themselves. By following these steps and remaining open to feedback, it is possible to create an effective tool for improving the mental health of teenagers. This review paper explores the various aspects of creating a web application to address teen depression with eating disorders and other mental health-related problems. The paper outlines the steps involved in the development process, including conducting research, defining the problem, developing a plan, building the application, testing it, launching and promoting it, and monitoring and evaluating its performance.

Future prospects

To develop a smoother and versatile application and a better personalized network among medical professionals and the teenagers. We also tend to abolish the stigma surrounding the mental health disorders and therapies. We hope to support and uplift the upcoming psychologists in India professionally by connecting them with the suffering individuals. Our application will be the perfect platform for spreading awareness about the mental health problems and the solutions and treatments which are already available for it. Teenagers will come to know that their problems can be solved and they can lead a normal life.

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